

SUSTAINABLE MEDICAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH

PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS: A CASE STUDY OF THE GOVERNMENT SECONDARY SCHHOOOL, OGBIA, BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Background: The prevalence of dental fluorosis in certain parts of the globe has been found to be increasing. In contrast to these prevalence reports in these areas, there is little or no systematic epidemiological study evaluating dental fluorosis in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. We thus studied the prevalence of dental fluorosis among school children in Ogbia town, Ogbia local government of Bayelsa state, Nigeria and evaluated the role played by potential risk factors.

Method: A cross-sectional survey of 242 school children (106 males, 136 females) within the age group of 10 – 17 years using a multistage random sampling technique was done. A pre-tested questionnaire was used to assess exposure to various fluoride sources. Dental professionals examined all the children to determine the absence or presence of dental fluorosis, with the Dean's Index used for grading of the degrees of dental fluorosis. Bivariate associations were tested using Chi-squared tests and linear logistic regressions were used to determine the association between selected risk factors and the occurrence of dental fluorosis.

Result: The mouth prevalence of dental fluorosis among our study sample was 19% and the Community Fluorosis Index was 0.57. The principal factor associated with the presence of dental fluorosis was sachet water (OR: 2.00, 95% CI: 0.97 – 4.09, $p = 0.04$). No significant association was found between dental fluorosis and the consumption of sea fish, the use of fluoride supplements and the use of fluoride toothpaste.

Conclusion: Dental fluorosis is thus, not a public health problem in Ogbia town, Bayelsa state although, sachet water is a risk factor associated with the occurrence of dental fluorosis. Measures should thus be taken to review the fluoride content of sachet water produced in the area of this study. Also, similar in-depth studies using similar criteria for assessing dental fluorosis prevalence needs to be carried out in other parts of Bayelsa state and Nigeria as a whole.

INTRODUCTION

Fluoride is often called a double-edged sword because deficiency of fluoride intake leads to dental caries while excess intake leads to dental and skeletal fluorosis. (Esa & Razak, 2001).

There has been a decline in dental caries prevalence and incidence during the last two decades, both in economically developed and in economically developing countries. This decrease is considered to be largely due to the widespread use of fluoride. Concurrent with the decline in caries, an increase in the prevalence of dental fluorosis has been documented, in communities with and without fluoridated drinking water. (McGrady et al, 2012; Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001; [Mascarenhas](#), 2000).

Dental fluorosis is a developmental disturbance of dental enamel caused by successive exposures to high concentrations of fluoride during tooth development, leading to enamel with lower mineral content and increased porosity. The clinical appearance of mild dental fluorosis is characterized by bilateral, diffuse (not sharply demarcated) opaque, white striations that run horizontally across the enamel. These may be invisible to the individual and the clinician but often can be seen after the enamel has been dried. The opacities may coalesce to form white patches. In the more severe forms the enamel may become discolored and/or pitted. Upon eruption into the mouth, fluorosed enamel is not discolored; the stains develop over time due to the diffusion of exogenous ions (e.g., iron and copper) into the abnormally porous enamel. (Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001).

The severity of dental fluorosis depends on when and for how long the overexposure to fluoride occurs, the individual response, weight, degree of physical activity, nutritional factors as well as bone growth. The recommended level for daily fluoride intake is 0.05 – 0.07 mg F/Kg/day, which is considered of great help in preventing dental caries by acting during remineralization. (Abanto et al, 2009).

Abanto et al (2009) stated that some 10% of children in optimally fluoridated (1.0 ppm) areas were affected by mild or very mild fluorosis in the permanent teeth and that less than 1% were so affected in low-fluoride areas. These degrees of prevalence were recorded prior to the availability of fluoridated dental products when fluoridated drinking water was the only significant source of fluoride intake, although this was still the view of a study conducted in the United States on the prevalence of adolescent fluorosis among adolescents aged between 10-17 years, which showed that the main dietary source of fluoride was drinking water however other sources included the widespread use of fluoride drugs, fluoride tablets, mouth rinses, fluoride tooth pastes as well as various processed foods and beverages (Eugenio et al, 2010; WHO, 2002; [Mascarenhas](#), 2000). Children within the age bracket of 10 – 17 years usually represent a population at risk for dental fluorosis as the period of teeth calcification from infancy to 6 years of age constitutes the vulnerable period for the onset of dental fluorosis (Gopalakrishnan et al, 1999) with the period of greatest susceptibility being the time of mineralization of the secondary upper central incisor teeth at about 22 – 26 months of age. (WHO, 2004)

Many studies have also identified fluoride supplements as risk factors for dental fluorosis, both in fluoridated and non-fluoridated areas. In fluoridated areas the risk of dental fluorosis from use of fluoride supplements is almost 4 times higher than in non-fluoridated areas. (Buzalaf, Cury, & Whitford, 2001).

The prevalence of dental fluorosis has been increasing in a number of countries in recent years (Esa & Razak, 2001), it has been observed that there is insufficient or no data as regarding the prevalence of dental fluorosis in Bayelsa state. With the presence of what looks like a white-mottled appearance (which is suggestive of dental fluorosis) on the teeth of students in the Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state, it is thus suspected that dental fluorosis may be prevalent in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state.

Thus, this makes it necessary to determine whether or not this mottled appearance is due to dental fluorosis as well as to determine the presence of any associated risk factors.

This research work when completed will provide useful information about dental fluorosis in Ogbia local government area. It will educate communities in Ogbia as well as various health parastatals in Bayelsa state and in Nigeria at large on the prevalence of dental fluorosis in Ogbia local government area of Bayelsa state as well as possible ways to prevent future occurrences of dental fluorosis.

METHODS

We performed a cross-sectional survey of school children attending Basic Junior Secondary School and Government Secondary School, Ogbia within the age group of 10-17 years (JSS 1 – SS 3) during the month of February 2013.

Children in this age group were selected because they represent a population at risk for dental fluorosis; the period of calcification of teeth from infancy to 6 years of age constitutes the vulnerable period for the onset of this condition.

Ogbia town was chosen as the area of study because of unpublished reports indicating that dental fluorosis was prevalent in the area. The principal sources of drinking water in this area include sachet water (commonly known as pure water), tap water as well as water from boreholes.

The Taro Yamen's formula was used to calculate the sample size and a simple random cluster sampling technique was used to select our study sample after consultation with the principals of both schools as to the population of the study area. Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Principals of the participating schools and age eligibility requires that the subjects fall into the appropriate age bracket at the time of sampling.

The data were collected and recorded, based on a structured close-ended pre-tested questionnaire to obtain information on the age, gender, ethnicity and the religion of the respondents. Information on the source of drinking water, sea-fish intake, the use of fluoride supplements as well as the use of fluoride-containing toothpaste by the students was also gotten. These factors have been identified as potential risk factors for dental fluorosis in previous studies"

The printed questionnaires were administered to the students on the day of the dental examination, with clear instructions to submit the completed form as a pre-requisite for oral examination.

Oral examination

The oral examination of each student was carried out by a dental specialist in the concerned classroom with the subject seated in a chair in bright daylight and the teeth were not dried prior to the examination for fluorosis.

The presence and severity of dental fluorosis was recorded and the Dean's index (Dean H.T., 1942) was used to determine the grade of dental fluorosis, thus:

- *Unaffected*: The enamel is translucent. The surface of the tooth is smooth, glossy, and usually has a pale creamy white colour.
- *Questionable*: The enamel shows slight changes ranging from a few white flecks to occasional white spots. This classification is utilized in those instances in which a definitive determination of the mildest form of fluorosis is not warranted and a classification of unaffected is not justified.
- *Very mild*: Small opaque paper-white areas are scattered over the tooth surface, but do not involve as much as 25% of the surface.
- *Mild*: White opaque areas on the surface are more extensive, but do not involve as much as 50% of the surface.
- *Moderate*: White opaque areas affecting more than 50% of the enamel surface.
- *Severe*: All enamel surfaces are affected. The major aspect of this classification is the presence of discrete or confluent pitting.

Statistical Analysis

We estimated a sample size of 242 subjects for the present study.

The prevalence of dental fluorosis was estimated by summing the occurrences of dental fluorosis showing definite signs of the condition. This implies adding up the occurrences from very mild fluorosis to severe fluorosis.

Community Fluorosis Index (CFI) was derived by multiplying the numerical weight (statistic consideration: p) and the frequency of fluorosis and dividing the result by the total sample.

A community fluorosis index of greater than 0.6 had been used in previous studies to identify areas where fluorosis was a public health problem. (Saravanan S. et al, 2008)

The association of dental fluorosis (dependent variable) with select individual risk factors (predictor variables) was studied using chi-square tests. Linear logistic regressions were used to determine the association between selected risk factors and the occurrence of dental fluorosis.

A p-value of <0.05 was used for entry of the variables in the multivariable models. Odds ratios (and their 95% CI) for the association of the predictor variables with the dependent variable were computed.

All analyses were performed with the Epi Info statistical software and p-value of <0.05 was taken to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS

Altogether, 242 respondents were used in this study. The modal age was 13, n=58 (24%); 56.4% of the respondents were female, most of the respondents are of the Ijaw-speaking tribes of Nigeria: n=173 (71.5%) and majority of the respondents, n=232 (95.9%) are Christians. The demographic data of the respondents are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents (Subjects)

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. AGE			
10	7	2.90	1.20 – 5.90
11	9	3.70	1.70 – 6.90
12	36	14.90	10.60 – 20.00
13	58	24.00	18.70 – 29.90
14	47	19.40	14.60 – 25.00
15	44	18.20	13.50 – 23.60
16	19	7.90	4.80 – 12.00
17	22	9.10	5.80 – 13.40
2. GENDER			
MALE	106	43.60	37.20 – 50.10
FEMALE	136	56.40	49.90 – 62.80
3. ETHNIC GROUP			
IGBO	63	26.00	20.60 – 32.00
IJAW	173	71.50	65.40 – 77.10
YORUBA	6	2.50	0.90 – 5.30
4. RELIGION			
CHRISTIANITY	232	95.90	92.50 – 98.00
ISLAM	7	2.90	1.20 – 5.90
OTHERS	3	1.20	0.30 – 3.60

N= 242

AGE RANGE: 10 – 17 YEARS; MODAL AGE: 13 (n = 58, 24.00%)

MEAN AGE: 13.85 ± 1.71; VARIANCE: 2.94

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SOURCES OF DRINKING WATER AS RISK FACTORS OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

In all, the consumption of five different sources of drinking water was determined. 122 (50.4%) of the respondents drink borehole water, 149 (61.6%) of the respondents drink sachet water (popularly known as pure water), 159 (65.7%) of the respondents consume tap water, 20 (8.3%) get their drinking water from wells and 20 (8.3%) also get their drinking water from the river. This is outlined in table 2.

Table 2: Sources of Drinking Water as a Risk Factor Of Dental Fluorosis

WATER SOURCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVALS
1. BOREHOLE			
• YES	122	50.40	43.90 – 56.90
• NO	120	49.60	43.10 – 56.10
2. SACHET WATER			
• YES	149	61.60	55.10 – 67.70
• NO	93	38.40	32.30 – 44.90
3. WELL WATER			
• YES	20	8.30	5.10 – 12.50
• NO	222	91.70	87.50 – 94.90
4. TAP WATER			
• YES	159	65.70	59.40 – 71.70
• NO	83	34.30	28.30 – 40.60
5. RIVER WATER			
• YES	20	8.30	5.10 – 12.50
• NO	222	91.70	87.50 – 94.90

OTHER RISK FACTORS OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

In this study, the presence of three other risk factors were used in determining the prevailing risk factor(s) associated with dental fluorosis in Government Secondary School, Ogbia town. 224 (92.6%) of the respondents use a fluoride-containing toothpaste, 143 (27.3%) of the respondents eat sea fish often and only 66 (27.3%) of the respondents use fluoride supplements. These are shown in table 3.

Table 3: Other Risk Factors of Dental Fluorosis

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. USE OF TOOTHPASTE			
• YES	224	92.60	88.50 – 95.50
• NO	18	7.40	4.50 – 11.50
2.FLUORIDE SUPPLEMENTS			
• YES	66	27.30	21.80 – 33.30
• NO	176	72.70	66.70 – 78.20
3. CONSUMPTION OF SEA FISH			
• YES	143	59.10	52.60 – 65.30
• NO	99	40.90	34.70 – 47.40

MOUTH PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS

After oral examination of the 242 subjects involved in this study, it was found that 150 (62%) of the subjects were not affected by dental fluorosis, 46 (19%) of them had questionable fluorosis, 15 (6%) of the subjects had very mild fluorosis, 9 (4) of them had mild fluorosis, 6 (2%) had moderate fluorosis and 16 (7%) of the subjects had severe fluorosis. This is shown in figure 1. In calculating the prevalence of dental fluorosis the Dean’s Index was used with the prevalence of dental fluorosis considering only cases with definite signs of fluorosis ranging from very mild fluorosis to severe fluorosis. The attainment of the Community Fluorosis Index was based on Dean’s (1942) Index score (0 – 4.0for dental fluorosis. This is shown in table 4.

FIGURE 1: PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS AMONG STUDENTS AGED BETWEEN 10 – 17 ATTENDING GOVERNMENT SECONDARY SCHOOL, OGBIA.

Table 4: Dean’s Index to Determine Prevalence of Dental Fluorosis and Community Fluorosis Index In Students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

	FREQUENCY OF FLUOROSIS	PERCENTAGE (%)	WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS	FREQUENCY*WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS
UNAFFECTED	150	62	0	0
QUESTIONABLE	46	19	0.5	23
VERY MILD	15	6	1	15
MILD	9	4	2	18
MODERATE	6	2	3	18
SEVERE	16	7	4	64
TOTAL	242	100		138

NOTE: THE PREVALENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS CONSIDERS ONLY CASES WITH DEFINITE SIGNS OF FLUOROSIS RANGING FROM VERY MILD FLUOROSIS TO SEVERE FLUOROSIS(REFERENCE ON INDEX).

FROM TABLE ABOVE:

PREVALENCE OF FLUOROSIS = SUMMATION (FREQUENCIES OF VERY MILD, MILD, MODERATE AND SEVERE FLUOROSIS)

$$= 15 + 9 + 6 + 16$$

COMMUNITY FLUOROSIS INDEX

THIS IS EQUAL TO:

$$= \frac{\text{SUMMATION (FREQUENCY OF FLUOROSIS * WEIGHT OF FLUOROSIS)}}{\text{TOTAL SAMPLE}}$$

$$= \frac{138}{242}$$

$$= 0.57 \text{ (BORDERLINE FOR PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE)}$$

COMPARISON BETWEEN FLUOROSIS AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS

The Chi-squared test as well as bivariate associations was used to determine a relationship between fluorosis and the risk factors stated in this study. This is shown in table 5.

Table 5: Odds Ratio Estimation For Prevalence Of Fluorosis And Risk Factors In Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

RISK FACTOR p-value	ODDS RATIO FOR DENTAL		CONFIDENCE INTERVAL	
	FLUOROSIS	PREVALENCE	INFERIOR	SUPERIOR
TAP WATER	1.41	0.70	2.85	0.21
RIVER WATER	0.45	0.10	2.01	0.22
BOREHOLE WATER	0.57	0.30	1.10	0.06
SATCHET WATER*	2.00	0.97	4.09	0.04
FLUORIDE TOOTHPASTE	2.00	0.43	8.82	0.30
FLUORIDE SUPPLEMENTS	1.38	0.69	2.75	0.23
SEA FISH CONSUMPTION	0.90	0.46	1.68	0.41

**STUDENTS THAT CONSUMED SATCHET WATER (PURE WATER) HAD 2 TIMES MORE RISK TO SUFFER DENTAL FLUOROSIS THAN THOSE WHO DID NOT CONSUME IT. (Chi²: 3.64;p-value: 0.04.*

THIS IS THE SAME CASE WITH FLUORIDE TOOTHPASTE ALTHOUGH THE p-Value DOES NOT SHOW STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE (p-value: 0.30)

DISCUSSION

The low prevalence and Community Fluorosis Index suggests that dental fluorosis is not a public health problem in the study area.

The overall prevalence of fluorosis of 19% is less than what was recorded by Gopalakrishnan et al (35.6%). This finding was the same for the community fluorosis index which was lower than previous findings: 0.57 as against 0.69 (Gopalakrishnan et al, 1999). This thus shows that dental fluorosis is less of a public health problem in our study area than in other regions (Chandrashekar J. et al, 2004) although the number of severe cases (n=16 [7%]) evokes some concern as it may have been due to a chronic ingestion of excessive fluoride by these students.

On examination of the subjects, the major complication of dental fluorosis was the presence of white opacities (89.13%) while the remainder (10.87%) presented with pitting/chipped-off enamel which were all seen as severe cases of dental fluorosis.

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Sachet water commonly called pure water (in this part of the world) was found to be a statistically significant risk factor associated with dental fluorosis with an odds ratio value of 2.00 (Confidence Interval: 0.97 – 4.09, Chi²: 3.64, p-value:0.04). Unfortunately, there are no prior reports to associate with this finding.

It was also observed that fluoride-containing toothpaste was a major risk factor associated with the occurrence of dental fluorosis with an odds ratio value of 2.00 (although this result was not statistically significant, p-value: 0.30). This however, is supported by previous findings in which it has been reported that excessive fluoride intake due to inadequate use or swallowing of fluoride-containing toothpaste is also responsible for the development of dental fluorosis. (Abanto et al, 2009). Other risk factors tested in this study were however less likely to cause dental fluorosis.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, dental fluorosis is not a public health problem among students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia town; although, the number of observed severe cases of the disease should be treated as urgent cases of public health intervention.

Sachet water (pure water) is a significant risk factor of dental fluorosis among students of Government Secondary School, Ogbia.

It is recommended that further in-depth research using similar criteria for assessing the prevalence of dental fluorosis in other parts of Bayelsa state and Nigeria as a whole be done. A review of the fluoride content of sachet water by its manufacturers is also advised and oral health education on the principles guiding the usage of fluoride-containing toothpaste should be looked into to be carried out.

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